

1 *Review*

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3 **Plant food extracts and phytochemicals: Their role as**
4 **Quorum Sensing Inhibitors**

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16 ABSTRACT

17 Traditionally, plant food extracts and phytochemical compounds have been used as
18 remedies against microbial infections with the added benefit that most of them are safe
19 for human consumption. These compounds have been also highlighted as *Quorum*
20 *Sensing Inhibitors* (QSI). *Quorum Sensing* (QS) is a regulatory mechanism that enables
21 bacteria to make collective decisions with respect to the expression of a specific set of
22 genes which can be related to virulence factors. Among all the available studies, most of
23 them use biosensor to demonstrate the role of plant foods and phytochemicals as QSI
24 and only few of these studies focus on their mechanisms of action. This review
25 summarizes the published scientific work on the use of plant food extracts and
26 phytochemicals as QSI, highlighting the techniques used to identify their biological
27 activity and their mechanisms of action.

28

29 *Keywords:* fruits; vegetables; antimicrobial; antipathogenic; bacterial
30 pathogenesis; bacteria communication; autoinducer.

31

32 1. Introduction

33 Since ancient times, plant food extracts and phytochemicals have been used in
34 nutrition and medicine mostly because of their range of beneficial effects against human
35 chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases and inflammation as well as their
36 antimicrobial activity. Plant food extracts and phytochemicals have been recognized as
37 effective treatments against microbial infections with the added benefit that most of
38 them are harmless for human health. However, in the last years, plant food extracts and
39 phytochemicals have also been highlighted as *Quorum Sensing* Inhibitors (QSI).
40 *Quorum Sensing* (QS) is a regulatory mechanism that enables bacteria to make
41 collective decisions with respect to the expression of a specific set of genes (Kalia,
42 2013). Several authors have demonstrated that QS regulate bacterial pathogenesis by
43 controlling competence development, sporulation, antibiotic synthesis, virulence factor
44 induction, cell differentiation, and nutrient flux along with other physiological events in
45 pathogenic bacterial infections (Greenberg, 2003). Atkinson and Williams (2009)
46 demonstrated that QS mechanisms amplify bacterial virulence by stimulating the
47 expression of disease causing attributes, such as motility, biofilm formation, and
48 secretion of virulence factors. In QS systems, bacteria produce low-molecular-weight
49 signaling compounds, known as autoinducers that are released into the environment.
50 The most widely studied signaling compounds include fatty acid derivatives, generally
51 *N*-acylhomoserine lactones (AHLs) used by Gram-negative bacteria, and a furanosyl
52 borate diester, autoinducer-2 (AI-2), which is used in interspecies communication
53 (Kalia, 2013). However, other molecules such as autoinducer-3 (AI-3), which activates
54 enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) virulence genes, and amino acids and short
55 peptides used by Gram-positive bacteria have been also identified as signaling
56 molecules (Kalia, 2013). QS signaling molecules serve to inter or intra bacteria species

57 communication but also modulate the host immune response. Previous exposure of the
58 host organism to QS molecules facilitated the survival of the infected host organism that
59 is able to increase the clearance of infecting bacteria (Bjarnsholt et al., 2005). In other
60 cases, exposure to QS signals before infection can extend the survival of the host but
61 also the persistence of the infection (Bandyopadhaya et al., 2012).

62 Many research studies have reported the capacity of plant extracts and
63 phytochemicals to interfere in intra- and inter-species QS communication systems
64 (Teplitski, Robinson & Bauer, 2000; Vandeputte, Kiendrebeogo, Rajaonson, Diallo,
65 Mol & Jaziri, 2010; Vattem, Mihalik, Crixell, & McLean, 2007). Actually, the ability of
66 plants to interrupt QS systems may serve as a defense mechanism to fight against
67 bacterial invasion. One of the keys of success of plant food extracts and phytochemicals
68 could be their similitude to what is considered the ideal QSI, which includes being
69 chemically stable, highly effective low-molecular-mass molecules and harmless for
70 human health (Rasmussen & Givskov, 2006). In fact, the consumption of these extracts
71 and phytochemicals are rarely associated with any side-effect as seen in many antibiotic
72 regimes. Additionally, plant food extracts and phytochemicals have also been
73 recognized to serve as novel food preservation techniques, although their use must be
74 selected in the specific system in which they are to function, as they cannot easily be
75 transferred from one QS system to another (Rasch et al., 2007).

76 The most commonly recognized mechanisms of action of plant food extracts and
77 phytochemicals are related to their similarity in chemical structure to QS signals and
78 also their ability to degrade signal receptors (Kalia, 2013). In the case of AHLs, the
79 proteins that act as receptors or regulators are known as the LuxR family of
80 transcriptional regulators, whereas AI-2-type QS is dependent on the activity of
81 LuxP/Q-type proteins. In this case, LuxP is a periplasmic-binding protein that binds AI-

82 2 (Reading & Sperandio, 2006). Nevertheless, there are other potential mechanisms of
83 action that plant food extracts and phytochemicals might use to inhibit bacterial QS
84 (Fig. 1). However, only few of the available studies focus on the role of plant food
85 extracts and phytochemicals as QSI deals with the potential mechanisms of action
86 (Kalia, 2013). Therefore, the main objective of this review is to summarize all the
87 scientific work focused on the use of plant food extracts and phytochemicals as QSI,
88 highlighting the techniques used to identify their biological activity and their
89 mechanisms of action.

90

91 **2. Methods for evaluation of plant food extracts and phytochemicals as QSI**

92 Some reviews have already addressed the role of these compounds as QSI,
93 although most of them have focused on dietary phytochemicals, medicinal plants, or
94 herbal plant extracts (Al-Hussaini & Mahasneh, 2009; Vandeputte et al., 2011). Fig. 2
95 shows the establishment of a network connection between the available literature on
96 plant food extracts (fruits, vegetables and fresh herbs and spices) included in this review
97 and the main parameters evaluated. In these studies, the QS inhibitory activity of plant
98 food extracts have been demonstrated using many different strategies, making the
99 comparison among studies very difficult. Most of them have determined the anti-QS
100 activity of these extracts using only biosensor strains and only few of them have used
101 chromatographic techniques (Fig. 2).

102 Biosensor strains activate a phenotypic response through an AHL-receptor protein
103 in presence of QSI as plant food extracts and phytochemicals. The first tool used to
104 screen for QSIs was a mutant strain (CV026) of the bacterium *Chromobacterium*
105 *violaceum*. *C. violaceum* constitutively produces the purple pigment violacein whereas
106 its mutant strain CV026 only synthesizes the pigment in response to the exogenously

107 added AHLs, 3-oxo-*N*-hexanoyl homoserine lactone (3-oxo-C6-HSL) and *N*-hexanoyl
108 homoserine lactone (C6-HSL) (Bjarnsholt, van Gennip, Jakobsen, Christensen, Jensen,
109 & Givskov, 2010). Fig. 3 shows a representative image of a biosensor test using *C.*
110 *violaceum*, which shows the inhibition of the violacein production in the presence of a
111 QS inhibitor. Based on the *gfp*-based AHL sensor system Rasmussen et al. (2005)
112 developed a system by electroporation of a plasmid (pTBR2iB) into a strain of *E. coli*,
113 known as QSIS1. The QSIS1 comprise a gene encoding a lethal protein fused to a QS-
114 controlled promoter and therefore, it is unable to growth if a QSI is not present in the
115 growth media. Hence, a positive screen with this system is indicated by the growth of
116 the selector bacteria. Another very well-known biosensor is *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*
117 NT1 (Ravn et al., 2001). Since the different monitor strains do not detect the same
118 spectra of AHL, the simultaneous use of different biosensor strains has been
119 recommended (Ravn et al., 2001). On the other hand, *Vibrio harveyi* is the AI-2
120 biosensor most commonly used (Rasmussen & Givskov, 2006). The bacteria biosensors
121 provide a simple, rapid, and sensitive means to detect QS inhibitors without requiring
122 any sophisticated instrumentation but they do not allow quantitation. However,
123 unequivocal chemical analysis and quantification of signaling compounds in bacterial
124 culture supernatants by chromatographic techniques such as LC-MS/MS spectrometry
125 provide more accurate and comparable data (Truchado et al., 2012a).

126

127 **3. Plant food extracts**

128 Plant food extracts from many different botanical groups (e.g. fruits, vegetables
129 and fresh herbs and spices) have been confirmed as strong QSI (Kalia, 2013).
130 Otherwise, preclinical and clinical studies, as well as some epidemiological data have
131 revealed a potential relationship between the consumption of plant food extracts and a

132 range of health benefits (Arts & Hollman, 2005). The evidence of the antipathogenic
133 activity of plant food extracts by blocking the signaling network is more recent but
134 several powerful QSI have been identified to date (Jakobsen et al., 2012a; Truchado,
135 Gil, Tomás-Barberán, Larrosa & Allende, 2012a). Up to now, studies have been carried
136 out to demonstrate the anti-QS activity of plant food extracts such as fruits, vegetables
137 and fresh herbs and spices (Fig. 2).

138

139 3.1. *Fruits*

140 Fruits are an important part of the diet and contain phytochemical compounds
141 which exert some beneficial effects on human health, particularly on age-related
142 diseases, as well as antimicrobial activity (Heinonen, 2007). Fruit extracts have been
143 identified as novel candidates in the search of natural compounds that attenuate bacterial
144 pathogenesis by interfering with QS systems without affecting their viability (Truchado
145 et al., 2012b). The disruption of cell to cell communication by fruit extracts may reside
146 in the variety of their different phytochemicals that can mimic molecules with the QS
147 signal or accelerate their degradation (Vattem et al., 2007) (Fig. 1). Table 1 summarizes
148 research studies where fruit extracts have been proven as QSI against pathogenic and
149 spoilage bacteria excluding those studies which only evaluated the anti-QS activity by
150 biosensor strains.

151 The biological activities of berries are partially attributed to their high content of
152 phytochemicals such as flavonoids (anthocyanins, flavonols, and flavanols), tannins
153 (proanthocyanidins, ellagitannins, and gallotannins), stilbenoids (e.g., resveratrol),
154 phenolic acids (hydroxybenzoic and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives), and lignans
155 (Vattem et al., 2007). Different berries (cranberry, wild blueberry, raspberry, blackberry
156 and strawberry) and grapes showed QSI activity as AHL signal inhibitors in *C.*

157 *violaceum* but they also significantly reduced swarming motility in *E. coli* and
158 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 (Vattem et al., 2007). It could be hypothesized that
159 their activity as QSI could also be attributed to their phytochemical content. However,
160 in a recent study, strawberry and blueberry did not give a positive result with the QSI1
161 screen (Jakobsen et al., 2012a).

162 Many research studies have focused on the antimicrobial activity of pomegranate
163 (*Punica granatum*) extracts, including leaf, bark, fruit and seed extracts (Ismail, Sestili,
164 & Akhtar, 2012). Although the capacity of pomegranate as QSI has received much less
165 attention, some papers have already demonstrated the anti-QS capacity of pomegranate
166 using the biosensor strain *C. violaceum* (Koh & Tham, 2011; Truchado et al., 2012a).
167 Additionally, the ability of pomegranate to inhibit the AHL system of pathogenic
168 bacteria such as *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Erwinia carotovora* has been evidenced.
169 Truchado et al. (2012a) demonstrated that the reduction of AHL production by
170 pomegranate was partially due to the degradation-transformation of AHLs (Fig. 1).

171 Apple extract (Fратиanni, Coppola, & Nazzaro, 2011) has also demonstrated anti-
172 QS activity against *C. violaceum* in a dose-dependent manner. Musthafa, Ravi,
173 Annapoorani, Packiavathy, and Pandian (2010) demonstrated that the aqueous extract of
174 pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) and saponilla (*Manilkara zapota*) fruits were able to
175 inhibit the AHL system in *C. violaceum* CV026 as well as in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1,
176 affecting violacein and pyocyanin pigment production, staphylolytic protease, elastase
177 production and biofilm formation, respectively. Apricot (*Prunus armeniaca*) also
178 showed anti-QS activity against the biosensor strains *C. violaceum* CV026 and *P.*
179 *aeruginosa* PAO1 inhibiting violacein production and swarming motility, respectively
180 (Koh & Tham, 2011).

181 Recently, Truchado et al. (2012b) showed the capacity of an orange extract, rich
182 in flavanones, to reduce the levels of 3-Oxo-C6-HHL and C6-HHL excreted to
183 extracellular media and biofilm formation by *Y. enterocolitica*. These phenotypic
184 responses were associated with the induction of two important QS regulatory genes,
185 *yenR* and *flhDC*, which are involved in the synthesis and regulation of AHLs and
186 motility in *Y. enterocolitica*, respectively. On the other hand, grapefruit juice was able to
187 inhibit AHLs and AI-2 activities of *V. harveyi* BB886 and BB170 strains as well as the
188 biofilm activity of pathogenic bacteria such as, *E. coli* O157:H7, *Salmonella*
189 *typhimurium* and *P. aeruginosa* (Girenavar et al., 2008). Several studies have not only
190 evaluated the antimicrobial and anti-QS activity of fruits and their extracts but they also
191 have tried to identify and isolate the bioactive compounds responsible for this activity
192 (Girenavar et al., 2008; Truchado et al., 2012a,b). The capacity of food phytochemicals
193 as QSI will be addressed later within this review.

194

195 3.2. Vegetable food extracts

196 The anti-QS capacity of different plant foods such as cauliflower, horseradish,
197 radish, bean sprout, carrot, pepper yellow, garden cress, water cress and canola was
198 explored using the biosensor QSI1 and other biosensor strains (Jakobsen et al., 2012a;
199 Rasmussen et al., 2005). Fig. 2 shows that research papers focused on the anti-QS
200 activity of vegetable food extracts use biosensors as main tool to detect QS inhibitors. In
201 this case, horseradish showed the highest activity against the biosensors *P. aeruginosa*
202 *lasB-gfp* and *P. aeruginosa rhlA-gfp*. Other *Brassicaceae* with anti-QS properties were
203 broccoli and cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea*) (Karamanoli & Lindow, 2006; Lee et al.,
204 2011a; Vатtem et al., 2007). Broccoli extracts not only reduced AI-2 synthesis, but also
205 swimming and swarming motility in *E. coli* O157:H7 in a dose-dependent manner (Lee

206 et al., 2011a). These authors were able to demonstrate that the broccoli extract was able
207 to regulate virulence in *E. coli* O157:H7 by modulating the transcription of virulence
208 genes. The broccoli extract was also able to protect a model organism (*Caenorhabditis*
209 *elegans*) against the pathogenic attack by the *E. coli* O157:H7 and based on that, it has
210 been proposed as an agent to attenuate bacterial virulence *in vivo* (Lee et al., 2011a).
211 However two important questions remain answered; what is the active compound in the
212 broccoli extract and whether the doses needed to decrease *E. coli* O157:H7 virulence in
213 the gut can be achieved through diet.

214 The ability of a methanolic extract of caper (*Capparis spinosa*) as QSI has been
215 demonstrated using the biosensor *C. violaceum* (Issac-Abraham, Palani, Ramaswamy,
216 Shunmugiah, & Arumugam, 2011). This extract was also effective regulating virulence
217 factors in pathogenic and spoilage bacteria such as swimming and swarming motility,
218 exopolysaccharide production (EPS) and biofilm in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1, *E. coli*,
219 *Proteus mirabilis* and *Serratia marcescens* in a dose-dependent manner, without
220 affecting the bacterial growth (Table 1). In fact, in a previous work, a vanilla extract
221 (rich in vanillic acid) showed violacein pigment inhibition activity in a dose-dependent
222 manner (Choo, Rukayadi, & Hwang, 2006). However, vanilla did not give a positive
223 result with the QSI1 screen (Jakobsen et al., 2012a). Leaves, flowers, fruit and bark of
224 sowthistle (*Sonchus oleraceus*) exhibited anti-QS activity in the *C. violaceum* plate
225 assay (Al-Hussaini & Mahasneh, 2009).

226 Seed and seedling exudates seem to be very active as QSI. For instance, seeds
227 from pea, rice, soybean and tomato were identified as QSI against different biosensor
228 strains (Teplitski et al., 2000). According to this, pea seeds and seedlings and their
229 extracts and exudates were effective inhibiting violacein production (*C. violaceum*) and
230 also swimming and swarming motility in *Serratia liquefaciens* MG1 and *P. aeruginosa*

231 PAO1, respectively (Fatima, Zahin, Khan, & Ahmad, 2010; Teplitski et al., 2000).
232 Several studies have concluded that one potential mechanism of action could be due to
233 the presence of AHL mimic molecules able to disrupt the QS system in biosensor
234 bacteria (Pérez-Montaña et al., 2013) (Fig. 1). Teplitski et al. (2000) also reported that
235 exudates from pea seedlings contain several compounds that mimicked AHL signals in
236 several bacterial reporter strains affecting the AHL-regulated gene expression probably
237 at AHL receptor level. On the other hand, seeds, seedlings and exudates of alfalfa
238 (*Medicago sativa* and *Medicago truncatula*) exhibited anti-QS activity, inhibiting
239 violacein production in *C. violaceum* (CVO26) and modulatory activity of LuxR (*E.coli*
240 pSB401), LasR (*E.coli* pSB1075), LuxP (*V. harveyi* BB170), AhyR (*E.coli* pSB536)
241 and CviR (*C. violaceum* CVO26) genes (Gao, Teplitski, Robinson,& Bauer, 2003;
242 Keshavan, Chowdhary, Haines, & Gonzalez, 2005). However, the extract of fenugreek
243 (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) increased pigment production in *C. violaceum* and
244 swarming motility in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 (Fatima et al., 2010).

245 Antimicrobial properties of garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) have been known since
246 ancient times and probably for this reason it is the plant food whose anti-QS properties
247 have been most studied. Garlic extract reduced the QS response of LuxR, AhyR and
248 TraR reporter strains in *E. coli* and *A. tumefaciens* (Bodini, Manfredini, Epp, Valentini,
249 & Santori, 2009). In *P. aeruginosa*, fresh garlic extract inhibited the production of
250 extracellular virulence factors such as alginate, pyoverdine, haemolysin and
251 phospholipase C (Harjai, Kumar, & Singh, 2010). Bjarnsholt et al (2005) showed that
252 garlic-treated biofilms of *P. aeruginosa* provoked *in vitro* an oxidative burst in human
253 polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMNs) whereas non garlic-treated biofilm or *P.*
254 *aeruginosa* QS-deficient mutant biofilms did not produce PMNs activation. The *in vivo*
255 activity of garlic was demonstrated in mice, prophylactically treated with a garlic

256 extract. In this study, the mortality rate of mice with pulmonary infection of *P.*
257 *aeruginosa* was reduced, probably due to the activation of PMN in the lung tissue which
258 caused an increased bacterial clearance. Harjai et al. (2010) also found a decrease in the
259 incidence of pyelonephritis caused by *P. aeruginosa* in mice prophylactically treated
260 with garlic; although little is known about the real implication of QS systems in these
261 phenomena.

262

263 3.3. Fresh herbs and spices

264 Fresh herbs and spices are rich in phytochemicals with antimicrobial activity and
265 therefore potential anti-QS compounds. Lately, several studies have focused on proving
266 the potentiality of fresh herbs and spices as anti-QS extracts. For instance, clove extracts
267 (*Syzygium aromaticum*) showed inhibition of QS activity in the *C. violaceum* CVO26,
268 *E. coli* pSB401 and *E. coli* pSB1075 biosensors (Krishnan, Yin, & Chan, 2012). In fact,
269 most of the studies used biosensors to demonstrate the anti-QS activity of these extracts.
270 Table 2 shows the low number of research studies where fresh herbs and spices have
271 been proven as QSI against pathogenic and spoilage bacteria. In *P. aeruginosa* PAO1,
272 clove extract also decreased gene expression of *lecA* virulence factor, pyocyanin
273 formation and swarming motility (Krishnan et al., 2012). Mexican sage (*Salvia*
274 *mexicana*) exhibited AHL mimic activity in biosensor strains (*A. tumefaciens* and *C.*
275 *violaceum*) (Karamanoli & Lindow, 2006). In a screening of many herbs and spices it
276 was found that basil, kale, oregano, thyme, rosemary, ginger, and turmeric extracts
277 inhibited violacein pigment production (*C. violaceum*) and decreased swarming motility
278 of *E. coli* O157:H7 and *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 (Al-Hussaini & Mahasneh, 2009; Vattem
279 et al., 2007). According to this, thyme and rosemary decreased *Listeria monocytogenes*
280 cell attachment to PVC, biofilm growth, development and metabolic activity (Sandasi,

281 Leonard, & Viljoen, 2010). Jakobsen et al. (2012a) have also described a QS-inhibitory
282 activity in the biosensor QSI1 for thyme and rosemary extracts as well as for chervil
283 and lemon grass extracts. *Ocimum sanctum* leaf extract, also known as holy basil, laurel
284 (*Laurus nobilis*) and two pepper species (*P. nigrum* and *P. longum*) also exhibited anti-
285 QS activity against a biosensor strain (*C. violaceum*) (Al-Hussaini & Mahasneh, 2009;
286 Musthafa et al., 2010; Tan et al., 2013). When tested against the opportunistic pathogen
287 *P. aeruginosa* PAO1, holy basil also decreased total proteolytic activity and LasB
288 elastase activity (Musthafa et al., 2010).

289

290 4. Food Phytochemicals

291 Plants have an almost limitless ability to synthesize aromatic substances, most of
292 which are phenols or their oxygen-substituted derivatives. Most are secondary
293 metabolites, of which at least 12,000 have been isolated, a number estimated to be less
294 than 10% of the total (Wink, 2010). In many cases, these substances serve as plant
295 defence mechanisms against predation by microorganisms, insects, and herbivores.
296 Some, such as terpenoids, give plants their odors; others (quinones and anthocyanins)
297 are partly responsible for plant pigment. Many compounds are responsible for plant
298 flavor (e.g., the terpenoid capsaicin from chili peppers), and some of the same herbs and
299 spices used by humans to season food yield useful medicinal compounds (Wink, 2010).
300 On the other hand, the ability of plants to produce substances that affect QS regulation
301 may provide plants with important tools to manipulate gene expression and behaviour in
302 the bacteria they encounter. In fact, eukaryotic organisms are able to produce and
303 secrete compounds that mimic the QS signals of bacteria and thus affect the behaviour
304 of associated bacteria (Bauer & Robinson, 2002).

305 Food phytochemicals have been found to act as QSI not only because of the
306 similarity in their chemical structure to those of QS signals (AHL) but also because of
307 their ability to degrade signal receptors (LuxR/LasR) (Teplitski, Mathesius, &
308 Rambaugh, 2011; Truchado et al., 2012a) (Fig. 1). Table 3 summarizes the research
309 studies where food phytochemicals have been proven as QSI against pathogenic and
310 spoilage bacteria, excluding those studies which only evaluated the anti-QS activity by
311 biosensor strains.

312 Furanocoumarins are a class of organic chemical compounds produced by a wide
313 variety of plants like grapefruit, lime, lemon, parsley and celery. They are
314 biosynthesized partly through the phenylpropanoid pathway and the mevalonate
315 pathway. Girenavar et al. (2008) reported that two furocoumarins (bergamottin and
316 dihydroxybergamottin, Fig. 4), isolated from grapefruits, had strong AI-1 and AI-2
317 inhibitory activities at concentration as low as 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. They were also able to inhibit
318 biofilm formation in *E. coli* O157:H7, *S. typhimurium* and *P. aeruginosa*.

319 Limonoids are also important constituents of the grapefruit and other citrus fruits.
320 Limonin, nomilin, obacunone (Fig. 4), deacetyl nomilin and limonin 17-O- β -D-
321 glucopyranoside are the predominant limonoids present in the grapefruit (Fig. 4). These
322 limonoids are characterized by a high degree of oxygenation and the presence of a furan
323 ring, similar to that present in the autoinducer molecules HAI-1 and AI-2 from *V.*
324 *harveyi*. Vikram, Jesudhasan, Jayaprakasha, Pillai, & Patil, (2010a, 2011a) studied the
325 potential effects of limonoids, such as obacunone as QSI and concluded that they
326 interfere with *V. harveyi* and EHEC cell–cell signalling and biofilm formation by
327 modulating the response regulator LuxO and type three secretion systems (TTSS),
328 respectively. Further work examined the potential of five citrus limonoids: isolimonic
329 acid, ichangin, isoobacunoic acid, Isoobacunoic acic glucoside and deacetyl nomilinic

330 acid glucoside, to inhibit EHEC biofilm and TTSS. All the tested limonoids seem to
331 interfere with the EHEC biofilm formation in a dose-dependent manner, isolimonic acid
332 being the strongest QSI among all the tested limonoids (Vikram, Jesudhasan, Pillai, &
333 Patil, 2012). One thing in common between furocoumarins and limonoids is that they
334 share a furan moiety with the synthetic furanones, very well- known because of their
335 QSI abilities.

336 As previously mentioned, garlic possesses a very well-known antimicrobial
337 activity. Persson, Hansen, Rasmussen, Skinderso, Givskov, and Nielsen (2005)
338 identified several active compounds from garlic extracts that exhibited LuxR antagonist
339 activity in *Vibrio fischeri* and *P. aeruginosa* PAO1, cyclic thioacetal and cyclic
340 disulphide being the most effective compounds. Another compound present in garlic
341 extracts is pyrogallol, which showed antagonism activity against AI-2 mediated QS in
342 *V. harveyi* in a micromolar range without any cytotoxic effect (Ni, Choudhary, Li, &
343 Wang, 2008). Ajoene, a sulphur-rich molecule from garlic, has been proven as a QSI
344 against *P. aeruginosa* (Fig. 4). Jakobsen et al. (2012b) reported a dose-dependent
345 attenuation of a few but central QS-controlled virulence factors in this opportunistic
346 bacteria. These authors stated that ajoene is the major QSI compound in the garlic
347 extract and demonstrated that this compound inhibited genes controlled by QS in *P.*
348 *aeruginosa*.

349 Among the different phytochemical compounds that can be found in cinnamon
350 (*Cinnamomum verum*), cinnamaldehyde (Fig. 4) is a good candidate to inhibit bacterial
351 QS systems. Niu, Afre and Gilbert (2006) were the first to demonstrate the ability of
352 cinnamaldehyde to inhibit both AI-1 and AI-2 receptor systems in the *V. harveyi* BB886
353 and BB170 strains. Later, Brackman et al. (2008) concluded that this compound affected
354 the target protein LuxR in *V. harveyi*. They also showed the potential of

355 cinnamaldehyde to inhibit biofilm formation in two *Vibrio mutants*, (*V. anguillarum*
356 4411 and *V. vulnificus LMG*) concluding that cinnamaldehyde affected the total mass of
357 the biofilm, which is related to the production/accumulation of the exopolysaccharide
358 matrix, but not the number of viable cells present in the biofilm.

359 Polyphenols, best known for their antioxidant properties, have been shown to have
360 an effect on QS systems. Huber, Eberl, Feucht, and Polster (2003) investigated the anti-
361 QS activity of three polyphenols ((-)-epigallocatechin, ellagic acid and tannic acid, Fig.
362 3) reporting that the three compounds showed antagonistic effect in two AHL-
363 dependent QS strains (*Pseudomonas putida* (pKR-C12) and *E. coli* MT102). In this
364 study, epigallocatechin and ellagic acid also produced a marked reduction in biofilm
365 thickness of *Burkholderia cepacia*. Matsunaga et al. (2010) also studied potential
366 inhibitory effect of eight catechins on biofilm formation of *Eikenella corrodens*, a
367 periodontopathogenic bacterium. They concluded that catechins with the galloyl group,
368 inhibited biofilm formation, more efficiently than those with the pyrogallol-type B-ring,
369 through the interference with the AI-2-mediated QS system. Truchado et al. (2012a)
370 evaluated the capacity of several food phytochemicals as QSI against spoilage (*E.*
371 *carotovora*) and pathogenic bacteria (*Y. enterocolitica*). This study evidenced the
372 capacity of many different phytochemical compounds such as cinnamaldehyde, ellagic
373 acid, resveratrol and rutin among others to interfere with the QS system of spoilage and
374 pathogenic bacteria. The observed interference was due to both the degradation-
375 transformation of AHLs and the inhibition of AHL synthesis (Fig. 1). According to this,
376 Wang, Lai, Hsueh, Chiou, Lin, and Liaw (2006) reported the inhibitory effect of
377 resveratrol on swarming and virulence factor expression (haemolysin, urease) of *P.*
378 *mirabilis*, an important pathogen infecting the urinary tract. Yuan et al. (2007) reported
379 that salicylic acid, which occurs in some fruits and vegetables, besides its well-known

380 function in regulating plant defence; it can also interfere directly with several aspects of
381 the *Agrobacterium* infection process. This phenolic plant secondary metabolite
382 specifically inhibited the expression of the *Agrobacterium virA/G* two-component
383 regulatory system that tightly controls the expression of the *vir* regulon including the
384 *repABC* operon on the Ti plasmid. Flavonoids have been the focus of research for many
385 years mainly due to their role as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer agents.
386 Keeping in view these health benefits, flavonoids such as naringenin (Fig. 4),
387 hesperidin, kaempferol, sinensetin, quercetin and apigenin have been evaluated for their
388 anti-QS activities. Vikram, Jayaprakasha, Jesudhasan, Pillai, and Patil (2010b) reported
389 a potential modulation of bacterial cell–cell communication, EHEC biofilm and *V.*
390 *harveyi* virulence, by flavonoids especially naringenin, quercetin, sinensetin and
391 apigenin. In a recent study, it was reported that naringenin attenuated *S. typhimurium*
392 virulence and cell motility by the repression of 24 genes in the *Salmonella* pathogenicity
393 island 1 and the down-regulation of 17 genes involved in flagellar biosynthesis and
394 motility (Vikram et al., 2011b). Kaempferol and quercetin, as well as the broccoli
395 compound myricetin, also reduced the expression of *flhD* and *eae* genes related to
396 flagella regulation and type III secretion in EHEC (Lee et al., 2011a). Therefore, one of
397 the mechanisms underlying the anti-QS activity of these compounds could be the
398 modulation of the expression of virulence-associated genes. The flavonoids catechin,
399 isolated from *Combretum albiflorum*, and naringenin reduced the production of QS-
400 mediated virulence factors (pyocyanin, elastase and biofilm formation) by *P.*
401 *aeruginosa* PAO1 (Vandeputte et al., 2010, 2011). According with these results,
402 catechin and naringin, an *O*-glycosylated flavanone, modulated the expression of the
403 QS-regulated genes (*lasI*, *lasR*, *rhlI*, *rhlR*, *lasA*, *lasB*, *phzA1* and *rhlA*) in *P.*
404 *aeruginosa* PAO1 and (*yenI*, *yenR*, *flhDC*, *fleB*, *fliA*) *Y. enterocolitica*, (Truchado et al.,

405 2012b; Vandeputte et al., 2011). Another flavonoid with potential QSI activity is
406 phloretin, a type of polyphenol mainly found in apples. Lee et al. (2011b) investigated
407 the ability of phloretin to control biofilms of *E. coli* O157:H7 as well as five commensal
408 *E. coli* strains, finding that phloretin specifically reduced *E. coli* O157:H7 biofilm
409 formation. DNA microarray and qRT-PCR studies showed that phloretin suppressed AI-
410 2 importer genes (*IsrACDBF*) of *E. coli* O157:H7 biofilm cells. This result supported
411 previous findings showing that flavonoids could interfere with bacterial QS signaling
412 and reduced *E. coli* O157:H7 biofilm formation (Lee et al., 2011b; Vikram et al. 2010b).
413 L-canavanine (Fig. 4), a non-proteinogenic α -amino acid, arginine analogue, found in
414 certain leguminous plants like alfalfa. Keshavan et al. (2005) identified L-canavanine,
415 as responsible for the inhibition of violacein production and the expression of the *exp*
416 genes in the Gram negative bacterium *Sinorhizobium meloti*, and responsible for the
417 production of EPS II, a QS-regulated phenotype. Curcumin (Fig. 4), the major
418 constituent of turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) has been reported to reduce QS-mediated
419 virulence factors such as biofilm formation, total protease and elastase activities and
420 pyocyanin production, as well as to decrease 3-oxoC12-HSL and C4-HSL production in
421 *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 (Rudrappa & Bais, 2008). Moreover, curcumin was able to
422 decrease mortality rates in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *C. elegans* infected with *P.*
423 *aeruginosa*. The transcriptome analysis of *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 revealed that 43 genes
424 related to QS were modulated by curcumin (Rudrappa & Bais, 2008). Acylphenols,
425 including malabaricones B and C, are usually extracted from plants of the genus
426 *Myristica*, and are present in our diet through the consumption of nutmeg (*Myristica*
427 *fragans*). Recently, Chong et al. (2011) demonstrated the ability of malabaricone C, a
428 methanol-soluble compound, to inhibit violacein production (*C. violaceum*) as well as
429 the QS-regulated pyocyanin production and biofilm formation in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1.

430 Vanillin (4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde), a well-known food flavoring agent, (Fig.
431 4) is a phenolic aldehyde which is the primary component of the extract of the vanilla
432 bean (*Vanilla planifolia*). This compound has been recognized as a potential QSI
433 compound for *A. hydrophila* biofilms without affecting cell growth in different
434 membranes, including microfiltration, ultrafiltration, and reverse osmosis membranes
435 (Kappacherya, Paulb, Yoonc, & Kweonb, 2010). Moreover, the results of these studies
436 revealed that vanillin probably interferes with AHL by restricting the availability of
437 AHL to cells and thus prevents the initiation of the QS mechanism for biofilm
438 formation. Vanillin was studied for its QSI property against different individual AHL
439 molecules using bio indicator strains. Vanillin also showed significant inhibition in
440 short-chain (C4-HSL and 3-Oxo-C8-HSL) and long-chain AHL molecules Vanillin was
441 also able to reduce AHL production of C4-HSL, 3-Oxo-C8-HSL and long-chain AHL
442 molecules in biosensor strains (Ponnusamy, Paul, & Kweon, 2009). Phenylacetic acid
443 (PAA) (Fig. 4) is an organic compound considered as a very active auxin (a type of
444 plant hormone), which can be predominantly found in fruits. The capacity of this
445 compound to interfere with QS has been recently reported due to its capacity for
446 reducing the production of AHL-dependent factors in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 (pyocyanin,
447 exopolysaccharide, and protease and elastase production) (Musthafa, Sivamaruthi,
448 Pandian, & Ravi, 2012). In swimming inhibition assay, PAA-treated PAO1 cells
449 exhibited poor motility in swimming agar plate, while in *in vivo* analysis, PAO1-
450 preinfected *C. elegans* showed enhanced survival when treated with PAA. The chemical
451 compound PAA shows a structural similarity with the previously reported anti-QS
452 compound salicylic acid (Bandara, Zhu, Sankaridurg, & Willcox, 2006; Yang et al.,
453 2009; Yuan et al., 2007). Thus, based on this similarity, the inhibitory activity of PAA

454 might be due to the inhibition of AHL-regulated behaviors by binding competitively to
455 the AHL receptor protein (Musthafa et al., 2012) (Fig. 1).

456 In a screening of 13,000 samples containing different compounds purified from
457 whole plants and separated parts such as fruits, leaves, roots and stems, ursolic acid
458 (Fig. 4) was identified as a new biofilm inhibitor (Ren, Zuo, González–Barrios, Bedzyk,
459 Eldridge, & Pasmore, 2005). In this study, ursolic acid was able to decrease biofilm
460 formation in *E. coli*, *V. harveyi*, and *P. aeruginosa* PAO1. The analyses of the gene
461 expression profile by DNA microarrays of *E. coli* treated with ursolic acid showed an
462 up-regulation of genes implicated in chemotaxis, mobility and heat shock response
463 functions as well as a down-regulation of genes involved in cysteine synthesis and
464 sulphur metabolism. On the other hand, ascorbic acid, a natural QS analogue, decreased
465 the concentration of AI-2 and caused a reduction on sporulation and enterotoxin
466 production in the anaerobic foodborne pathogen *Clostridium perfringens* (Novak &
467 Fratamico, 2004).

468 Farnesol (Fig. 4) is a sesquiterpene commonly found in citrus fruits. However, the
469 anti-QS activity of farnesol has been mostly studied because this compound is also
470 produced by the fungus *Candida albicans*, which frequently coexists with the
471 opportunistic pathogen *P. aeruginosa*. It has been demonstrated that both, *C. albicans*
472 and *P. aeruginosa*, are able to modulate the virulence of each other and therefore, their
473 QS mechanisms. Extracellular addition of farnesol to *C. albicans* reduced its biofilm
474 formation (Ramage, Saville, Wickes, & López–Ribot 2002), decreased transcript levels
475 of *pqsA* (the first gene in the PQS biosynthetic operon), and modulated hyphal
476 formation-associated genes (*TUP1*, *CRK1*, and *PDE2*) as well as others genes related to
477 drug resistance (*FCR1* and *PDR16*), cell wall maintenance (*CHT2* and *CHT3*), iron
478 transport (e.g. *FTR2*) and genes encoding heat shock proteins (*HSP70*, *HSP90*, *HSP104*,

479 CaMSI3, and SSA2 (Cao et al., 2005). In *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, farnesol inhibited
480 *in vitro* and also *in vivo* biofilm formation in a mouse model showing also a synergistic
481 effect with nafcillin and vancomycin antibiotic treatments (Pammi, Liang, Hicks,
482 Barrish, & Versalovic, 2011). It was also reported that *Pneumocystis spp* and
483 *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms were inhibited by farnesol treatment (Cushion, Collins,
484 & Linke, 2009; Jabra-Rizk, Meiller, James, & Shirtliff, 2006). Cugini, Morales, and
485 Hogan, (2010) showed that addition of farnesol to the growing medium of *LasR*-
486 defective *P. aeruginosa* strains restored the PQS and therefore, the virulence factor
487 pyocyanin. Sesquiterpene lactones are sesquiterpenoids that contain a lactone ring that
488 can be found in many plants. Thymoquinone (Fig. 4) is a phytochemical compound
489 found in the plant *Nigella sativa* L., commonly known as black seed or black cumin and
490 native to south and southwest Asia. Thymoquinone showed a significant inhibitory
491 effect on biofilm formation of *S. epidermidis*, *S. aureus* and *Enterococcus faecalis* in a
492 dose-dependent manner (Chaieb, Kouidhi, Jrah, Mahdouani, & Bakhrouf, 2011).

493 Riboflavin, also known as vitamin B2, and lumichrome, a derivative of the
494 riboflavin have been reported to act as QS signal-mimic compounds, capable of
495 stimulating the *P. aeruginosa* LasR QS receptor (Rajamani et al., 2008). These authors
496 concluded that riboflavin and lumichrome could serve as either QS signals or as inter-
497 kingdom signal mimics capable of manipulating QS in bacteria with a LasR-like
498 receptor. However, lumichrome has very little structural similarity to AHLs and its
499 identification as a compound capable of stimulating the LasR AHL receptor is quite
500 unexpected, suggesting the possibility that AHL receptors might recognize more than
501 one kind of compound (Holden et al., 1999).

502 Iberin, an isothiocyanate produced by many members of the *Brassicaceae* family,
503 was found to be a QSI of *P. aeruginosa* (Jakobsen et al., 2012a), interfering with the

504 LasIR and RhlIR systems and down regulating the QS-controlled rhamnolipid
505 production.

506

507 **5. Health benefits and beyond**

508 It has been hypothesized that the use of food phytochemicals and extracts as QSI
509 may be of therapeutic interest since regular consumption of these products may exert
510 some modulatory *in vivo* effects on the intestinal microbiota and prevent the invasion of
511 pathogens (Giménez-Bastida et al., 2012). Contrariwise, Jakobsen et al. (2012a)
512 explained that based on their experience, it is unlikely that any natural food source has
513 biologically relevant amounts of QSIs sufficient to be considered for therapeutic
514 purposes but they may have a role as preventative therapies in individuals affected by
515 bacterial infections, for whom a diet enriched in QSI might show prophylactic
516 properties. According to this, Truchado et al. (2012b) showed that a natural orange
517 extract enriched in flavanones (mainly naringin, neohesperidin, and hesperidin), at doses
518 that can be achieved in the gut through the diet, exhibits a moderate antipathogenic
519 activity against *Y. enterocolitica* by reducing the production of AHLs and the formation
520 of biofilm.

521 It should be also taken into account that bioactive compounds present in plant
522 food extracts and phytochemicals are metabolized by the gut and colon microbiota
523 yielding new metabolites that might influence not only the presence of pathogenic
524 bacteria but also modulate microbiota population groups by either enhancing the growth
525 of beneficial bacteria or causing their depletion. In the search for natural products that
526 may improve intestinal health by reducing the ability of pathogens to invade the
527 intestine or increasing beneficial bacteria groups it is essential to investigate the effects

528 of the actual metabolites that are formed *in vivo*. A recently published paper explored
529 the impact of the microbiota derived ellagitannins (ETs) metabolites, urolithin-A and
530 urolithin-B, on the intestinal pathogen *Y. enterocolitica* cell–cell signaling (Giménez-
531 Bastida et al., 2012). On the other hand, the ETs derived metabolite urolithin-A was
532 able to modulate gut microbiota by increasing bifidobacteria and lactobacilli
533 populations in an ulcerative colitis rat model (Larrosa et al., 2010). The ability of these
534 metabolites to inhibit QS controlled biofilm formation, motility and the production of
535 AHLs as well as to increase beneficial microbiota highlights the potential role of QS as
536 a modulator of pathogenic bacteria and also of gut microbiota, although nowadays, we
537 are not aware of studies that focus on the implication of the QS system to modulate gut
538 microbiota populations. These results warrant further investigation of the *in vivo*
539 antipathogenic properties of plant derived metabolites and their effect on gut
540 microbiota.

541

542 **6. Conclusions**

543 In food vegetables and fruits there are a great variety of compounds, most of them
544 still unidentified, that are part of our diet and that their consumption, in quantities
545 achievable through diet, is safe. These compounds have a great potential to inhibit
546 bacterial QS systems and thus to mitigate bacterial pathogenesis. The mechanisms of
547 action of these QSI compounds are varied, from the competition with the autoinducer
548 for the receptor to the modulation of genes involved in virulence, but this is not
549 surprising given the high variability of phytochemicals in our diet. Some studies have
550 already shown a protective effect of these compounds against pathogenic bacterial
551 invasion of living organisms. However, more *in vivo* studies are required to give rise to

552 consistent results in bacterial pathogenesis and QS inhibition. Plant extracts and
553 phytochemicals constitute a very promising tool for the management of bacterial
554 pathogenesis and gut microbiota modulation.

555

556 **Acknowledgments**

557 This work has been supported by the COST ACTION FA1202 BacFoodNet and by
558 CONSOLIDER INGENIO 2010, CSD2007-00063 (Fun-C-Food). P. Truchado holds a
559 post-doctoral fellowship of the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness. I.
560 Castro-Ibáñez is the holder of a JAE-PreDoc contract from the CSIC.

561 We thank Inge Van der Linden for her assistance in figures elaboration.

562

563 **References**

- 564 Al-Hussaini, R. & Mahasneh, A.M. (2009). Microbial growth and quorum sensing
565 antagonist activities of herbal plants extracts. *Molecules*, *14*(9), 3425–3435.
- 566 Arts, I.C., & Hollman, P.C. (2005). Polyphenols and disease risk in epidemiologic
567 studies. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, *81*(1sup), 317S–325S.
- 568 Atkinson, S., & Williams, P. (2009). Quorum sensing and social networking in the
569 microbial world. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, *6*(40), 959–978.
- 570 Bandara, M.B., Zhu, H., Sankaridurg, P.R., & Willcox, M.D. (2006). Salicylic acid
571 reduces the production of several potential virulence factors of *Pseudomonas*
572 *aeruginosa* associated with microbial keratitis. *Investigative Ophthalmology and*
573 *Visual. Science*, *47*(10), 4453–4460.
- 574 Bandyopadhyaya, A., Kesarwani, M., Que, Y.A., He, J., Padfield, K., Tompkins, et al.
575 (2012). The quorum sensing volatile molecule 2-amino acetophenon modulates
576 host immune responses in a manner that promotes life with unwanted guests.
577 *PLoS Pathogens*, *8*(11), e1003024.
- 578 Bastian, M., Heymann, S., & Jacomy, M. (2009). Gephi: an open source software for
579 exploring and manipulating networks. International AAAI Conference on
580 Weblogs and Social Media.
- 581 Bauer, W.D., & Robinson, J.B. (2002). Disruption of bacterial quorum sensing by other
582 organisms. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, *13*(3), 234–237.
- 583 Bjarnsholt, T., Jensen, P.Ø., Rasmussen, T.B., Christophersen, L., Calum, H., Hentzer,
584 M., et al. (2005). Garlic blocks quorum sensing and promotes rapid clearing of
585 pulmonary *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infections. *Microbiology*, *151*(12), 3873–
586 3880.

587 Bjarnsholt, T., van Gennip, M., Jakobsen, T.H., Christensen, L.D, Jensen, P.Ø., &
588 Givskov, M. (2010). In vitro screens for quorum sensing inhibitors and in vivo
589 confirmation of their effect. *Nature Protocols*, 5(2), 282–293.

590 Bodini, S.F., Manfredini, S., Epp, M., Valentini, S., & Santori, F. (2009). Quorum
591 sensing inhibition activity of garlic extract and p-coumaric acid. *Letters in*
592 *Applied Microbiology*, 49(5), 551–555.

593 Brackman, G., Defoirdt, T., Miyamoto, C., Bossier, P., Calenbergh, S.V., Nelis, H., et
594 al. (2008). Cinnamaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde derivatives reduce virulence in
595 *Vibrio spp.* by decreasing the DNA-binding activity of the quorum sensing
596 response regulator LuxR. *BMC Microbiology*, 8(1), 149–162.
597 <http://dx.doi:10.1186/1471-2180-8-149>

598 Cao, Y.Y., Cao, Y.B., Xu, Z., Ying, K., Li, Y., Xie, Y., et al. (2005). cDNA microarray
599 analysis of differential gene expression in *Candida albicans* biofilm exposed to
600 farnesol. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 49(2), 584–589.
601 [http://dx.doi: 10.1128/AAC.49.2.584-589.2005](http://dx.doi:10.1128/AAC.49.2.584-589.2005)

602 Chaieb, K., Kouidhi, B., Jrah, H., Mahdouani, K., & Bakhrouf, A. (2011). Antibacterial
603 activity of Thymoquinone, an active principle of *Nigella sativa* and its potency
604 to prevent bacterial biofilm formation. *BMC Complementary and Alternative*
605 *Medicine*, 13, 11–29. [http://dx.doi: 10.1186/1472-6882-11-29](http://dx.doi:10.1186/1472-6882-11-29).

606 Chong, Y.M., Yin, W.F., Ho, C.Y., Mustafa, M.R, Hadi, A.H., Awang, K., et al. (2011).
607 Malabaricone C from *Myristica cinnamomea* exhibits anti-quorum sensing
608 activity. *Journal of Natural Products*, 74(10), 2261–2264. [http://dx.doi:](http://dx.doi:10.1021/np100872k)
609 [10.1021/np100872k](http://dx.doi:10.1021/np100872k).

610 Choo, J.H., Rukayadi, Y., & Hwang, J.K. (2006). Inhibition of bacterial quorum sensing
611 by vanilla extract. *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 42(6), 637–641.

612 Cugini, C., Morales, D.K., & Hogan, D.A. (2010). *Candida albicans*-produced farnesol
613 stimulates *Pseudomonas* quinolone signal production in LasR-defective
614 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains. *Microbiology* 156(10), 3096–3107. doi:
615 10.1099/mic.0.037911-0.

616 Cushion, M.T., Collins, M.S., & Linke, M.J. (2009). Biofilm formation by
617 *Pneumocystis spp.* *Eukaryotic Cell*, 8(2), 197–206.

618 Fatima, Q., Zahin, M., Khan, M.S., & Ahmad, I. (2010). Modulation of quorum sensing
619 controlled behavior of bacteria by growing seedling, seed and seedling extracts
620 of leguminous plants. *Indian Journal of Microbiology*, 50(2), 238–242.

621 Fratianni, F., Coppola, R., & Nazzaro, F. (2011). Phenolic composition and
622 antimicrobial and anti-quorum sensing activity of an ethanolic extract of peels
623 from the apple cultivar Annurca. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 14(9), 957–963.

624 Gao, M., Teplitski, M., Robinson, J.B., & Bauer, W.D. (2003). Production of substances
625 by *Medicago truncatula* that affect bacterial quorum sensing. *Molecular Plant-
626 Microbe Interactions*, 16(9), 827–834.

627 Giménez-Bastida, J.A., Truchado, P., Larrosa, M., Espín, J.C., F.A. Tomás-Barberán,
628 F.A., Allende, A., et al. (2012). Urolithins, ellagitannin metabolites produced by
629 colon microbiota, inhibit Quorum Sensing in *Yersinia enterocolitica*: Phenotypic
630 response and associated molecular changes. *Food Chemistry* 132 (3), 1465–
631 1474. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.12.003>

632 Girenavar, B., Cepeda, M.L., Soni, K.A., Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P., Jayaprakasha,
633 G.K., et al. (2008). Grapefruit juice and its furocoumarins inhibits autoinducer
634 signaling and biofilm formation in bacteria. *International Journal of Food
635 Microbiology*, 125(2), 204–208.

- 636 Greenberg, E.P. (2003). Bacterial communication and group behavior. *Journal of*
637 *Clinical Investigation*, 112(9), 1288–1290.
- 638 Harjai, K., Kumar, R., & Singh, S. (2010). Garlic blocks quorum sensing and attenuates
639 the virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *FEMS Immunology and Medical*
640 *Microbiology*, 58(2), 161–168.
- 641 Heinonen, M. (2007). Antioxidant activity and antimicrobial effect of berry phenolics a
642 Finnish perspective. *Molecular Nutrition and Food Research*, 51(6), 684–691.
- 643 Holden, M.T., Ram-Chhabra, S., de Nys, R., Stead, P., Bainton, N.J., Hill, P.J., et al.
644 (1999). Quorum-sensing cross talk: isolation and chemical characterization of
645 cyclic dipeptides from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and other gram-negative
646 bacteria. *Molecular Microbiology*, 33(6), 1254–1266.
- 647 Huber, B., Eberl, L., Feucht, W., & Polster, J. (2003). Influence of polyphenols on
648 bacterial biofilm formation and quorum-sensing. *Zeitschrift fur Naturforschung*
649 *C*, 58(11-12), 879–884.
- 650 Ismail, T., Sestili, P., & Akhtar, S. (2012) Pomegranate peel and fruit extracts: a review
651 of potential anti-inflammatory and anti-infective effects. *Journal of*
652 *Ethnopharmacology*, 143(2), 397–405. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2012.07.004.
- 653 Issac–Abraham S.V., Palani, A., Ramaswamy, B.R., Shunmugiah, K.P., & Arumugam,
654 V.R. (2011). Antiquorum sensing and antibiofilm potential of *Capparis spinosa*.
655 *Archives of Medical Research*, 42(8), 658–668.
- 656 Jabra–Rizk, M.A., Meiller, T.F., James, C.E., & Shirtliff, M.E. (2006). Effect of
657 farnesol on *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilm formation and antimicrobial
658 susceptibility. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 50(4), 1463–1469.
- 659 Jakobsen, T.H., Bragason, S.K., Phipps, R.K., Christensen, L.D., van Gennip, M.,
660 Alhede, M., et al. (2012a). Food as a source for quorum sensing inhibitors:

661 iberin from horseradish revealed as a quorum sensing inhibitor of *Pseudomonas*
662 *aeruginosa*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 78(7), 2410–2421.

663 Jakobsen, T.H., van Gennip, M., Phipps, R.K., Shanmugham, M.S., Christensen, L.D.,
664 Alhede, M., Skindersoe, M.E., et al. (2012b). Ajoene, a sulfur-rich molecule
665 from garlic, inhibits genes controlled by quorum sensing. *Antimicrobial Agents*
666 *and Chemotherapy*, 56(5), 2314–2325. <http://dx.doi:10.1128/AAC.05919-11>

667 .Kalia, V.C. (2013). Quorum sensing inhibitors: an overview. *Biotechnology Advances*,
668 31(2), 224–245. <http://dx.doi:10.1016/j.biotechadv.2012.10.004>.

669 Kappacherya, D., Paulb, D., Yoonc, J., & Kweonb, J.H. (2010). Vanillin, a potential
670 agent to prevent biofouling of reverse osmosis membrane. *Biofouling* 26(6),
671 667–672. <http://dx.doi:10.1080/08927014.2010.506573>.

672 Karamanoli, K., & Lindow, S.E. (2006). Disruption of *N*-acyl homoserine lactone-
673 mediated cell signaling and iron acquisition in epiphytic bacteria by leaf surface
674 compounds. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 72(12), 7678–7686.

675 Keshavan, N.D., Chowdhary, P.K., Haines, D.C., & Gonzalez, J.E. (2005). L-
676 Canavanine made by *Medicago sativa* interferes with Quorum Sensing in
677 *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 187(24), 8427–8436.

678 Koh, K.H. & Tham, F.Y. (2011). Screening of traditional Chinese medicinal plants for
679 quorum-sensing inhibitors activity. *Journal of Microbiology Immunology and*
680 *Infection*, 44(2), 144–148.

681 Krishnan, T., Yin, W.F., & Chan, K.G. (2012). Inhibition of quorum sensing–controlled
682 virulence factor production in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 by Ayurveda
683 spice clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) bud extract. *Sensors*, 12(4), 4016–4030.

684 Larrosa, M., González-Sarrías. A., Yáñez-Gascón, M.J., Selma, M.V., Azorín-Ortuño,
685 M., Toti, S., et al. (2010). Anti-inflammatory properties of a pomegranate extract

686 and its metabolite urolithin-A in a colitis rat model and the effect of colon
687 inflammation on phenolic metabolism. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*,
688 *21(8)*, 717-725. <http://dx.doi:10.1016/j.jnutbio.2009.04.012>

689 Lee, J.H., Regmi, S.C., Kim, J.A., Cho, M.H., Yun, H., Lee, C.S., et al. (2011b). Apple
690 flavonoid phloretin inhibits *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 biofilm formation and
691 ameliorates colon inflammation in rats. *Infection and Immunity* *79(12)*, 4819–
692 4827.

693 Lee, K.M., Lim, J., Nam, S., Yoon, M.Y., Kwon, Y.K., Jung, B.Y., et al. (2011a).
694 Inhibitory effects of broccoli extract on *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 quorum
695 sensing and in vivo virulence. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, *321(1)*, 67–74.

696 Matsunaga, T., Nakahara, A., Minnatul, K.M., Noiri, Y., Ebisu, S., Kato, A., et al.
697 (2010). The inhibitory effects of catechins on biofilm formation by the
698 periodontopathogenic bacterium, *Eikenella corrodens*. *Bioscience*,
699 *Biotechnology and Biochemistry*, *74(12)*, 2445–2450.

700 Musthafa, K.S., Ravi, A.V., Annapoorani, A., Packiavathy, I.S., & Pandian, S.K.
701 (2010). Evaluation of anti-quorum-sensing activity of edible plants and fruits
702 through inhibition of the N-acyl-homoserine lactone system in
703 *Chromobacterium violaceum* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Chemotherapy*
704 *56(4)*, 333–339.

705 Musthafa, K.S., Sivamaruthi, B.S., Pandian, S.K., & Ravi, A.V. (2012). Quorum
706 Sensing Inhibition in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 by Antagonistic
707 Compound Phenylacetic Acid. *Current Microbiology*, *65(5)*, 475–480.

708 Ni, N., Choudhary, G., Li, M., & Wang, B. (2008). Pyrogallol and its analogs can
709 antagonize bacterial quorum sensing in *Vibrio harveyi*. *Bioorganic and*

710 *Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 18(5), 1567–1572. <http://dx.doi:>
711 10.1016/j.bmcl.2008.01.081.

712 Niu, C., Afre, S., & Gilbert, E.S. (2006). Subinhibitory concentrations of
713 cinnamaldehyde interfere with quorum sensing. *Letters of Applied Microbiology*,
714 43(5), 489–494.

715 Novak, J.S. & Fratamico, P.M. (2004). Evaluation of Ascorbic Acid as a Quorum–
716 Sensing Analogue to Control Growth, Sporulation, and Enterotoxin Production
717 in *Clostridium perfringens*. *Journal of Food Science*, 69(3), 72–78. <http://dx.doi:>
718 10.1111/j.1365-2621.2004.tb13374.x

719 Pammi, M., Liang, R., Hicks, J.M., Barrish, J., & Versalovic, J. (2011). Farnesol
720 decreases biofilms of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and exhibits synergy with
721 nafcillin and vancomycin. *Pediatric Research*, 70(6), 578–583.

722 Pérez-Montaña, F., Jiménez-Guerrero, I., Sánchez-Matamoros, R.C., López-Baena, F.J.,
723 Ollero, F.J., Rodríguez-Carvajal, M.A., et al. (2013). Rice and bean AHL-mimic
724 quorum-sensing signals specifically interfere with the capacity to form biofilms
725 by plant-associated bacteria. *Research in Microbiology*, 164(7), 749–60.
726 <http://dx.doi:10.1016/j.resmic.2013.04.001>.

727 Persson, T., Hansen, T., Rasmussen, T., Skinderso, E., Givskov, M., & Nielsen, J.
728 (2005). Rational design and synthesis of new quorum–sensing inhibitors derived
729 from acylated homoserine lactones and natural products from garlic. *Organic and*
730 *Biomolecular Chemistry*, 3(2), 253–262.

731 Ponnusamy, K., Paul, D., & Kweon, J.H. (2009). Inhibition of quorum sensing
732 mechanism and *Aeromonas hydrophila* biofilm formation by vanillin.
733 *Environmental Engineering Science*, 26(8), 1359–1363.

734 Rajamani, S., Bauer, W.D., Robinson, J.B., Farrow, J.M., Pesci, E.C., Teplitski, M., et
735 al. (2008). The vitamin riboflavin and its derivative lumichrome activate the
736 LasR bacterial quorum-sensing receptor. *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions*,
737 *21*(9), 1184–1192. <http://dx.doi:10.1094/MPMI-21-9-1184>.

738 Ramage, G., Saville, S.P., Wickes, B.L., & López-Ribot, J.L. (2002). Inhibition of
739 *Candida albicans* biofilm formation by farnesol, a quorum-sensing molecule.
740 *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, *68*(11), 5459–5463.

741 Rasch, M., Rasmussen, T.B., Andersen, J.B., Persson, T., Nielsen, J., Givskov, M., et al.
742 (2007). Well-known quorum sensing inhibitors do not affect bacterial quorum
743 sensing-regulated beansprout spoilage. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, *102*(3),
744 826–837.

745 Rasmussen, T.B., Bjarnsholt, T., Skindersoe, M.E., Hentzer, M., Kristoffersen, P., Kôte
746 M., et al. (2005). Screening for quorum-sensing inhibitors (QSI) by use of a
747 novel genetic system, the QSI selector. *Journal of Bacteriology*, *187*(5), 1799–
748 1814.

749 Rasmussen, T.B., & Givskov, M. (2006). Quorum sensing inhibitors: a bargain of
750 effects. *Microbiology*, *152*(4), 895–904.

751 Ravn, L., Christensen, A.B., Molin, S., Givskov, M., & Gram, L. (2001). Methods for
752 acylated homoserine lactones produced by Gram negative bacteria and their
753 application in studies of AHL-production kinetics. *Journal of Microbiological*
754 *Methods*, *44*(3), 239–251.

755 Reading, N.C., & Sperandio, V. (2006). Quorum sensing: the many languages of
756 bacteria. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, *254*(1), 1–11.

757 Ren, D., Zuo, R., González-Barrios, A.F., Bedzyk, L.A., Eldridge, G.R., & Pasmore,
758 M.E. (2005). Differential gene expression for investigation of *Escherichia coli*

759 biofilm inhibition by plant extract ursolic acid. *Applied Environmental*
760 *Microbiology*, 71(7), 4022–4034.

761 Rudrappa, T., & Bais, H.P. (2008). Curcumin, a known phenolic from *Curcuma longa*,
762 attenuates the virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 in whole plant and
763 animal pathogenicity models. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*,
764 56(6), 1955–1962. <http://dx.doi:10.1021/jf072591j>.

765 Sandasi, M., Leonard, C.M., & Viljoen, A.M. (2010). The in vitro antibiofilm activity
766 of selected culinary herbs and medicinal plants against *Listeria monocytogenes*.
767 *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 50(1), 30–35.

768 Teplitski, M., Mathesius, U., Rambaugh, K.P. (2011). Perception and degradation of N–
769 acyl homoserine lactone quorum sensing signals by mammalian and plant cells.
770 *Chemical Reviews*, 111(1), 100–116.

771 Teplitski, M., Robinson, J.B., & Bauer, W.D. (2000). Plants secrete substances that
772 mimic bacterial N–acyl homoserine lactone signal activities and affect
773 population density–dependent behaviors in associated bacteria. *Molecular Plant-*
774 *Microbe Interactions*, 13(6), 637–648.

775 Truchado, P., Gil, A., Tomás-Barberán, F.A., Larrosa, M., Allende, A. (2012a). Food
776 phytochemicals act as Quorum Sensing Inhibitors reducing production and/or
777 degrading autoinducers of *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Erwinia Carotovora*.
778 *Food Control*, 24(1), 78–75.

779 Truchado, P., Giménez-Bastida, J.A., Larrosa, M., Castro-Ibáñez, I., Espín, J.C.,
780 García-Conesa, M.T. et al. (2012b). Inhibition of Quorum Sensing (QS) in
781 *Yersinia enterocolitica* by an Orange Extract Rich in Glycosylated Flavanones.
782 *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 60(36), 8885–8894.

783 Vandeputte O.M., Kiendrebeogo, M., Rasamiravaka, T., Stévigny, C., Duez, P.,
784 Rajaonson, S., et al. (2011). The flavanone naringenin reduces the production of
785 quorum sensing–controlled virulence factors in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1.
786 *Microbiology*, 157(7), 2120–2132.

787 Vandeputte, O.M., Kiendrebeogo, M., Rajaonson, S., Diallo, B., Mol, A., & Jaziri, M.E.
788 (2010). Identification of catechin as one of the flavonoids from *Combretum*
789 *albiflorum* bark extract that reduces the production of quorum–sensing–
790 controlled virulence factors in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1. *Applied*
791 *Environmental Microbiology*, 76(1), 243–253.

792 Vатtem, D.A., Mihalik, K., Crixell, S.H., & McLean, R.J.C. (2007). Dietary
793 phytochemicals as quorum sensing inhibitors. *Fitoterapia*, 78(4), 302–310.

794 Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P.R., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Pillai, B.S., & Patil, B.S. (2010a).
795 Grapefruit bioactive limonoids modulate *E. coli* O157:H7 TTSS and biofilm.
796 *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 140(2-3), 109–116. . [http://dx.doi:](http://dx.doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2010.04.012)
797 [10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2010.04.012](http://dx.doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2010.04.012).

798 Vikram, A., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Jesudhasan, P.R., Pillai, S.D., & Patil, B.S. (2010b).
799 Suppression of bacterial cell-cell signalling, biofilm formation and type III
800 secretion system by citrus flavonoids. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 109(2),
801 515–527. [http://dx.doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2672.2010.04677.x](http://dx.doi:10.1111/j.1365-2672.2010.04677.x)

802 Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P.R., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Pillai, B.S., Jayaraman, A., & Patil,
803 B.S. (2011b). Citrus flavonoid represses Salmonella pathogenicity island 1 and
804 motility in *S. typhimurium* LT2. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*
805 *145(1)*, 28–36.

806 Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P.R., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Pillai, S.D., & Patil, B.S., (2011a).
807 Citrus limonoids interfere with *Vibrio harveyi* cell–cell signalling and biofilm

808 formation by modulating the response regulator LuxO. *Microbiology* 157(1),
809 99–110. [http://dx doi: 10.1099/mic.0.041228-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1099/mic.0.041228-0).

810 Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P.R., Pillai, S.D., & Patil, B.S. (2012). Isolimononic acid
811 interferes with *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 biofilm and TTSS in QseBC and QseA
812 dependent fashion. *BMC Microbiology*, 12(1), 261. [http://dx.doi: 10.1186/1471-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1471-2180-12-261)
813 2180-12-261.

814 Walker, T.S., Bais, H.P., Déziel, E., Schweizer, H.P., Rahme, L.G., Fall, R., et al.
815 (2004). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*-Plant Root Interactions. Pathogenicity,
816 Biofilm Formation, and Root Exudation. *Plant Physiology*, 134(1), 320–331.

817 Wang, W.B., Lai, H.C., Hsueh, P.R., Chiou, R.Y., Lin, S.B., Liaw, S.J. (2006).
818 Inhibition of swarming and virulence factor expression in *Proteus mirabilis* by
819 resveratrol. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 55(10), 1313–1321.

820 Wink, M. (2010). Biochemistry of Plant Secondary Metabolism. In Wink, M. (Ed.)
821 *Annual Plant Reviews*, 40, Wiley-Blackwell, West Sussex, UK, pp. 1–17.

822 Yang, L., Theil–Rybtke, M., Jakobsen, T.H., Hentzer, M., Bjarnsholt, T., Givskov, M.,
823 et al. (2009). Computer–Aided Identification of Recognized Drugs as
824 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Quorum–Sensing Inhibitors. *Antimicrobial Agents*
825 *and Chemotherapy*, 53(6), 2432–2443.

826 Yuan, Z.C., Edlind, M.P., Liu, P., Saenkham, P., Banta, L.M., Wise, A.A., et al. (2007).
827 The plant signal salicylic acid shuts down expression of the vir regulon and
828 activates quorum–quenching genes in *Agrobacterium*. *Proceedings of the*
829 *National Academy of Sciences*, 104(28), 11790–11795.

830 **Table 1.** Vegetable food and fruits extracts proven as QSI against foodborne and spoilage bacteria.

Plant food or Fruit	Concentration	Target bacteria	Biological action	Mechanisms of action	Reference
Alfalfa seed exudate		<i>S. meliloti</i>	↓ EPS II secretion	AHL mimics	Keshavan et al., 2005
Pea seedlings extract,		<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ swarming motility	AHL mimics	Fatima et al., 2010
Pea	10 mg/mL	<i>S. liquefaciens</i> MG1	↓ swarming motility	AHL mimics	Teplitski et al., 2000
Broccoli	5%	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ AI-2 production	Supression of <i>LuxS pfs</i> and <i>fldh</i> mRNA	Lee et al., 2011
			↓ swarming motility	Decrease <i>ler</i> gene expression	
Caper	0.5-2 mg/ml	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ swimming motility	Inhibition of AHL	Isaac-Abraham <i>et al.</i> , 2011
		<i>P.mirabilis</i>	↓ swarming motility		
		<i>E. coli</i>	↓ EPS production		
		<i>S. marcescens</i>	↓ Biofilm formation		
Banana,		<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ swarming motility	AHL mimics	Fatima et al., 2010
Blueberry, raspberry, grape, blueberry, strawberry,	1%	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAOI	↓ motility inhibition		Vattem et al., 2007

blackberry, cranberry extracts		<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7			
Grapefruit juice		<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7 <i>S. typhimurium</i> <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	↓ AI-1 and AI-2 activities ↓ biofilm formation	Dihydroxybergamottin and bergamottin interfering with QS signaling	Girenavar et al., 2008
Orange extract	100-400 µg/mL	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	↓ 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL levels ↓ biofilm formation ↓ swimming motility	Degradation-transformation and inhibition of AHLs <i>yen R, flhDC</i> induction	Truchado et al., 2012b
Pineapple	2.5-10% (v/v)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAOI	↓ biofilm formation ↓ pyocyanidin production ↓ staphylolytic protease activity ↓ elastase activity	Unknown compounds that inhibit AHL mediated QS	Musthafa et al., 2010

Pomegranate	20 µg/mL	<i>E. carotovora</i>	↓ 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6-HSL levels	Degradation-transformation and inhibition of AHLs	Truchado et al., 2012a
		<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>			

831 3-oxo-C6HSL: *N*-3-oxo-hexanoyl-L-homoserine lactone; AHL: acyl-homoserine lactone; AI-1: autoinducer-1; AI-2: autoinducer-2; EPS: exopolysaccharide; QS: quorum

832 sensing; C6-HSL: *N*-hexanoyl-L-homoserine lactone; mRNA: messenger ribonucleic acid.

833 **Table 2.** Fresh herbs and spices proven as QSI against foodborne and spoilage bacteria.

Compound or extract	Concentration	Target bacteria	Biological action	Mechanisms of action	Reference
Clove extract	1-3 mg/mL	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ swarming motility ↓ pyocyanin production ↓ <i>LecA</i> gene expression		Krishnan et al., 2012
Ginger, oregano, thyme, kale, basil and turmeric extracts	5%	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ swarming motility		Vattem et al., 2007
Rosemary, thyme, and peppermint extracts	1 mg/mL	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	↓ PVC adhesion ↓ biofilm formation		Sandasi et al., 2009

834 AHL: acyl-homoserine lactone; LEE: locus of enterocyte effacement ; PVC: Polyvinyl chloride

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837 **Table 3.** Food compounds proven as QSI against foodborne and spoilage bacteria.

Compound or extract	Concentration	Target bacteria	Biological action	Mechanisms of action	Reference
Ajoene	0.085-0.34 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<p>↓ <i>rhlA</i>, <i>lasB</i> promoter activity</p> <p>↑ <i>tagQ1</i>, <i>tssB1</i>, <i>hcp1</i>, <i>exaC</i>, <i>PA0182</i> gene expression</p> <p>↓ <i>lasA</i>, <i>chiC</i>, <i>lecA</i>, <i>rhlA</i>, <i>rhlB</i>, <i>prpL</i>, <i>cbpD</i> gene expression</p> <p>↓ AHL levels</p> <p>↓ rhamnolipid production</p> <p>↑ bacterial clearance in infected mice</p>	Regulation of QS genes	Jakobsen et al., 2012b
Ascorbic Acid	30 mM	<i>C. perfringens</i>	<p>↓ AI-2 activity</p> <p>↓ spore production</p> <p>↓ enterotoxin production</p>	Interference with AI-2 activity	Novak & Fratamico, 2004
Catechin	4 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ pyocyanin production	Interference with AHL perception	Vandeputte et al., 2010

			↓ elastase activity		
			↓ biofilm formation		
			↓ <i>lasB</i> , <i>lasI</i> , <i>lasR</i> , <i>rhlA</i> , <i>rhlI</i> , <i>rhlR</i> gene expression		
Catechin gallate	0.1 mM	<i>E. corrodens</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Interference with AI-2 system	Matsunaga et al., 2010
Epicathechin gallate					
Gallocatechin gallate					
Epigallocatechin gallate					
Cinnamaldehyde and derivative compounds	0.1 mM	<i>V. anguillarum</i>	↓ protease activity	Reduction of LuxR binding to promoter	Brackman et al., 2008
			↓ pigment production		
			↑infected <i>Artemia</i> ssp. survival		
			↑antibiotic susceptibility		
Curcumin	0.003 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ pyocyanin production	Modulation of 716 genes	Rudrappa & Bais, 2008
			↓ biofilm formation		

			↓ protease, elastase activities			
			↓ AHL production			
			↓ infectivity on <i>A. thaliana</i> and <i>C. elegans</i>			
Dihydroxybergamottin and bergamottin	0.003 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7 <i>S. typhimurium</i> <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Inhibition of AI-1 and AI-2 activities		Girennavar et al., 2008
Ellagic acid	0.132 mM	<i>B. cepacia</i>	↓ biofilm formation	-		Huber et al., 2003
Ellagic acid	0.0132 mM	<i>E. carotovora</i> <i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	↓ AHL production	Degradation/transformation of AHLs		Truchado et al., 2012a
Epigallocatechin	0.13 mM	<i>B. cepacia</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Interference with AHLs		Huber et al., 2003
Epigallocatechin	0.25 mM	<i>E. corrodens</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Interference with AI-2 system		Matsunaga et al., 2010
Eriodictyol	4 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ pyocyanin production ↓ elastase activity	-		Vandeputte et al., 2011

Farnesol	0.25 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PA14	↓ pyocyanin production ↓ PQS levels	↓ <i>pqsA</i> transcript	Cugini et al., 2010
Gallocatechin	0.5 mM	<i>E. corrodens</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Interference with AI-2 system	Matsunaga et al., 2010
Iberin	0.6-1.22 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	↓ Rhl and Lux reporters ↓ rhamnolipid production ↓ <i>lasB</i> , <i>rhlA</i> gene expression	Modulation of 49 genes involved in QS	Jakobsen et al., 2012a
L-canavanine	0.00056 mM	<i>S. meliloti</i>	↓ <i>expE</i> gene expression ↓ EPS II secretion	-	Keshavan et al., 2005
Malabaricone C	2.8-8.4 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	↓ pyocyanin production ↓ biofilm formation	Interference with rhl and las QS systems	Chong et al., 2010
Naringenin	4 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ pyocyanin production ↓ elastase activity	Downregulation of QS genes Decrease AHLs production	Vandeputte et al., 2011
Naringenin	0.041-0.66 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ biofilm formation	Modulates AI-2 mediated	Vikram et al., 2010a

				signalling	
Naringin	0.34 mM	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	↓ biofilm formation ↓ swimming motility ↑ <i>yenR</i> gene expression	Decrease AHLs production	Truchado et al., 2012
Nomilin	0.01-0.1 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ biofilm formation	Competitive binding to receptor	Vikram et al., 2010b
Obacunone	0.11 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ biofilm formation	Competitive binding to receptor	Vikram et al., 2010b
Phenylacetic acid	1.47 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	↓ pyocyanin production ↓ EPS secretion ↓ protease, elastase activities ↓ swimming motility ↑ survival infected <i>C.elegans</i>	Competition with AHLs	Musthafa et al., 2012
Quercetin	0.02-0.33 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ biofilm formation	QS disruptor molecule	Vikram et al., 2010a
Resveratrol	0.087 mM	<i>E. carotovora</i> <i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	↓ AHL production	Degradation/transformation AHLs	Truchado et al., 2012

Resveratrol	0.065-0.13 mM	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ swarming motility ↓ flagellin productin ↓ haemolysin and urease activity ↓ cell invasion of urothelial cells 	RsbA-dependent inhibition	pathway	Wang et al., 2006
Riboflavine	0.04 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Activation of LasR QS receptor	Mimics AHL structure		Rajamani et al., 2008
Rosmarinic acid	0.03 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ biofilm formation			Walker et al., 2004
Salicylic acid	30 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ AHL production ↓ twitching and swimming motility ↓ protease activity ↓ invasion of corneal epithelial cells 	Decrease AHLs levels		Bandara et al., 2006
Salicylic acid	1.44 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ LasR, Rhl, Pqs activity ↓ proteolytic activity ↓ pyoverdine production ↓ rhamnolipid production 	LasR inhibition		Yang et al., 2009

			↓ biofilm formation		
Salicylic acid	0.006 mM	<i>A. tumefaciens</i>	↓ AHL production	Modulation of 103 genes some of them involved in virulence	Yuan et al., 2007
Sinenetin	0.017-0.27 mM	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7	↓ biofilm formation		Vikram et al., 2010a
Taxifolin	4 mM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	↓ pyocyanin production	Downregulation of QS genes	Vandeputte et al., 2011
			↓ elastase activity		
			↓ <i>lasI</i> , <i>lasR</i> , <i>lasA</i> , <i>lasB</i> , <i>rhlI</i> , <i>rhlR</i> , <i>rhlA</i> , <i>phzA1</i> gene expression		
Thymoquinone	0.13-0.5 mM	<i>S. aureus</i> <i>S. epidermidis</i> <i>E. faecalis</i>	↓ biofilm formation		Chaieb et al., 2011
Ursolic Acid	0.022 mM	<i>E. coli</i>	↓ biofilm formation		n et al., 2005
Vanillin	1 mM	<i>A. hydrophyla</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Inhibition of AHLs production	Ponnusamy et al., 2009
Vanillin	1.18 mM	<i>A. hydrophyla</i>	↓ biofilm formation	Interaction with AHL receptors	Kappacherya et al., 2010

838 AHL: acyl homoserine lactone; EPS: exopolysaccharide; PQS: 2-heptyl-3-hydroxy-4(1H)-quinolone; QS: quorum sensing.

839 **Figure captions**

840 **Fig. 1.** Scheme of the potential mechanisms of action of plant food extracts and
841 phytochemicals as QSI. The process of QS can be disrupted by reducing the activity of
842 AHL cognate receptor protein and/or AHL synthase (A) or inhibiting the production of
843 QS signal molecules by different mechanisms such as; (B) degradation of the AHL, (C)
844 sequestration of the AHL (D) mimicking the signal molecules primarily by using plant
845 food extracts and phytochemicals as analogues of signal molecules.

846 **Fig. 2.** Network showing the topics addressed in research papers focused on the anti-QS
847 activity of plant food extracts: fruits, food vegetables and fresh herbs and spices. Figure
848 was constructed with Gephi 0.8.2-beta software using the literature comprised in this
849 review. Gephi software reveals the underlying associations between objects, in
850 particular in scale-free networks representing patterns of biological data (Bastian,
851 Heymann, & Jacomy, 2009).

852 **Fig. 3.** Representative image of a biosensor test using *C. violaceum*, which shows the
853 inhibition of the violacein production when different concentrations of a QS inhibitor
854 compound are added to the culture media.

855 **Fig. 4.** Chemical structure of food phytochemicals showing anti-QS activity.

856

859 **Fig. 2.** (Colour reproduction on the Web)

860

861

862 **Fig. 3**

863

864 Fig. 4.

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866